

A STUDY REGARDING HEALTH THROUGH AYURVEDIC TECHNIQUE OF DAILY ROUTINE IN CHILDREN OF UPPER-PRIMARY LEVEL

Dr. Anita Jain *

ACADEMICIAN, DEPTT. OF EDUCATION, GOVERNMENT OF RAJASTHAN

Article

Received on 23 may 2016,
Revised on 26 may 2016,
Accepted on 29 may 2016

***Correspondence for
Author**

Dr. Anita Jain,
opp. Sandeepan Gurukul
school, Near ana sagar TT
college, Rangbari kota
Rajasthan pin 324005.

ABSTRACT

Ayurveda preventive medicine include Rasayan, Ritucharya & Dincharya Palan (follow Daily routine and seasonal routine according to ayurveda).

Present study was survey a study. A total of 100 subjects were enrolled, class 6 to 8 students of Govt. Upper Primary School, Suket Kota Rajasthan. They were interviewed and examine for health issue.

Present study show the importance of includes the basic knowledge of Dincharya, Ritucharya in class 6 to 8 syllabus. Result show that the decrease frequency of suffering from diseases through the regularly follow Dincharya.

KEYWORDS:

Ayurveda, awareness, child health, upper primary student ayurvedic daily routine, Dincharya

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda first aim is prevention and second is cure; universally known fact is prevention is better the cure. Ayurveda texts described many tools for prevention like Rasayan, Dincharya and Ritucharya, Ahar Vidhi Visheshaytan etc.

Dincharya Palan is plane for full day with use of some ayurvedic techniques like time of wake up, time of eating, what eat how eat when eat, hair cutting, nails cutting, brushing, Ushpan, Pratimarsha Nasya, Anjan and many other.

OBJECTIVE

The main objective of this study was to assess the importance of includes the basic knowledge of Dincharya, Ritucharya in class 6 to 8 syllabus.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study subjects

The study was conducted in the Govt. Upper Primary School, Suket Kota, Rajasthan, India. A total of 100 subjects were enrolled after written informed consent of parents in our study.

Groups

All 100 students are divided in two groups according the knowledge and interest showing in Dincharya.

Students of Group A are teach about Dincharya and basic knowledge of ayurveda techniques for prevention and group B form by these students they were not show interest in this Dincharya and basic knowledge of ayurveda techniques.

Study design and methods This study was a cross-sectional type of study. The aim was to study the importance of awareness on Dincharya Palan in health prevention in students of class 6 to 8.

Grouping was done on basis of basic knowledge of about the Dincharya and Ayurveda techniques.

Group A students have basic knowledge of about the Dincharya and Ayurveda techniques. Group B students have not basic knowledge of about the Dincharya and Ayurveda techniques. It confirm by interview.

Both groups were interviewed and examine for health issues by well qualified Ayurvedic doctor. Interviews were conducted on pre-designed and pretested questionnaires and checklist. Health examinations were conducted on

general health issue like checked level of immunity by frequency of suffering from disease, physical and mental health status. Data were collected and analyzed.

RESULTS

(1) Height and weight ratio-

Present study show that 60% normal height and weight ratio in group A and 24% in group B.

Table 1

Group	total students	normal height weight ratio	%
Group A	50	30	60
Group B	50	12	24

(2) Immunity level-

Present study show that 30% students of group A, had good immunity level, 50% medium immunity level and 20% low immunity level.

18% students of group B, had good immunity level, 34% medium immunity level and 48% low immunity level.

Table 2

Group	total	immunity level		
		goo	medi	low
Group A	50	15	25	10
Group B	50	9	17	24

Mental ability-

Group A – In these groups 40% students had good mental ability, 50% medium mental ability and 10% low mental ability.

Group B - In these groups 18% students had good mental ability, 34% medium mental ability and 48% students had low mental ability.

Table 3

Group	total	mental ability		
		good	medium	low
Group A	50	20	25	05
Group B	50	06	14	30

Physical ability-

Group A – In these groups 40% students had good physical ability, 50% medium physical ability and 10% low physical ability.

Group B - In these groups 18% students had good physical ability, 34% medium physical ability and 48% students had low physical ability.

Table 4

Group	total	physical ability (Bal Pariksha)		
		good	medium	low
Group A	50	17	18	15
Group B	50	11	14	25

DISCUSSION

Height and weight ratio, immunity level, mental ability and physical ability is more in Group A. Result show the importance of ayurvedic technique of daily routine in children. The age of that's children were 11 to 14 and average age were 12 year. All students were female. Reproductive organ maturation and secondary sex character start to develop in this age. If provide the nutrition and proper digestion done in this age, then development of child is very good. So this study should be doing on large number of students. Include the Ayurvedic technique of daily routine in syllabus of upper primary schools for better result and advance study.

REFERENCES:

1. Ashtanga Hridaya of Vagbhatta with Sarvanga Sundari, commentary by Pt. Vaidya Lal Chand Shastri, Motilal Banarsidas, First Edition (Rep.1977).
2. Bhela Samhita : Edited by Vaidya Visharad V.S Venkata Subramaniam Sastri and Vaidya Visharad Rajeshwar Sharma,1997.
3. Charaka Samhita by Agnivesha with Hindi Commentary by K.N.Shastri and G.N.Chaturvedi, Chaukhambha Vaidya Bhawan, Varanasi, 22nd Edition,1996.
4. Introduction to Kayachikitsa by C.Dwarkanatha second edition 1986 published by Chaukhambha Orientalia, P.O. 1032,Varanasi.
5. Sushruta Samhita by Maharishi Sushruta with Ayurveda Tattva Sandipika Commentary by Kaviraj Ambika Datt Shastri, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan,Varanasi,Eleventh Edition,1997.
6. Sarangadhar, “Sarangadhar Samhita”, Commentary by Prayagdutta Sharma, Chaukhambha Amar Bharati Prakashan, Varanasi, Khanda-1, (1988).